

Balancing Human Work Life –Challenges in IT sector

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Abstract

IT sector is a major sector in Industries contributing towards the economic growth of a country. India has a major contribution towards the economic growth through IT sector both inside as well as in foreign countries. Every year nearly 5.5% growth in the total GDP is observed from the IT industry. Such an industry is depending only on the human intelligence for the various IT products which are getting sold in the market. IT industry does not require any complicated machinery to be installed. All it needs is the human brain. IT Engineers are using their knowledge, skills for developing the IT products. Their working environment is not like any other production industries. They have always stressed in developing the IT products which should be delivered in time. The time limit given to the IT engineers is not sufficient. They have to be in connection with the clients, users, the company for which they develop the solution. They have to meet different kind of people with different psychologies in this process of development. These factors lead to psychological imbalance in the developers. This paper contains the working environment of the IT engineers, the amount of stress they have in the work place, and the amount of energy they put in the work place to get the product ready, This paper also explains a proposed model for such IT engineers as how to balance their work culture with the personnel life. This paper proposes the active involvement of IT engineers in social activities like music, dance and other form of arts for the refreshment of their brains as to improve the working efficiency.

Keywords: IT, IT Engineers, stress, management, work culture, balance

1 Introduction

IT sector in India is a major industry contributing to the overall growth of Indian economy. As of now the contribution of IT industry in Indian economy is nearly 13%. [1] IT sector in India started in the year 1967 in Mumbai. The famous company by then was TATA group which had the partnership with Burroughs. [2] Today we have several thousands of small scale, medium scale and large scale IT industries contributing to the economic development of India. IT sector is now divided into several sub sectors like IT development, IT services and BPO, Networking and hardware services. IT development industry involves people who are

creative knowledgeable and having minimum experience of three to five years in IT industry for development activities. They need to have good experience in development and management. They should have both technical as well as managerial skills in developing the IT product and delivering and training the end users. IT services need the people to provide the IT related services to the customers' problems. They need to be functional whenever the customer call them. They also need to have enough good knowledge in the IT industry to provide the service. BPO needs people with or without experiences to deal with the customers and transfer their complaints to the necessary departments.[3] [4]

Various IT solutions either in the form of development or in the form of service need only the skilled human resource. Here no other machine or technology can be replaced in the place of skilled human resource. Presently it is observed that all the IT Engineers are given a target to finish their work in such a way that they can not balance their personnel life with the work culture. They have to work day and night thinking the project which is given to them. All the time the developers or the service engineers get exhausted with the amount of the mental stress given to complete the project. [5] [6]

The result of this hectic mental stress based work will be the variation in the life style, various health issues and problems in personnel or family life. These engineers can not find time to spend with their family, children and society. It is very important to mingle with the children, family members and the society as it is told that in a life how much one earns is not important instead how does he lives in the society. Ones life not counted by his wealth instead his life is counted by his character, involvement in family and friends etc.

In addition to this imbalance in life his creativity starts reducing due to high mental pressures. This results in various health issues. It is very clear that if an engineer is not in a position to perform he will not be able to continue in his work. Ultimately an engineer who spends his talents, knowledge and creativity for the company has to leave the company one day for various issues. So it is very much important to balance ones life both to working environment as well as personnel life.[7]

2. Objective

The objective of this paper is to propose a model for the IT engineers to reduce the work pressure and increase the productivity.

3. Methodology

This paper proposes different activities for every IT engineer to balance the work life and thus to increase the productivity of the organization. Here some activities to be done inside the working environment to reduce the mental pressure of the IT engineer and activities to be after the working hours.

As we already know that IT is a profession wherein the human talent is only used for developing any IT solutions either in the form of a product or service. Here IT engineer has to utilize his knowledge and creativity. A person cannot concentrate for hours together like machine to concentrate on his work. This reduces the productivity of an organization. In order to improve the productivity, quality in the working environment the Engineer has to work in

peace so that his mind can work faster as well as can give him some innovative ideas in working environment.

To achieve this inside the working environment every IT engineer has to follow the following methods to improve the productivity.

Deep breathing: This is one method to reduce the stress and to relax inside the working environment. This not only reduces the stress but also slows down the heart beat reducing the higher blood pressure. This also relaxes the muscular system, neural system and mind will be ready to function in a better way. At least this activity should be repeated in every hour for nearly ten minutes.

Working environment should be soothing like availability of air, light and soft music which will improve the work efficiency.

Senior officials should not pressurize the engineers instead encourage them.

The life style of an IT engineer outside the working environment should be as shown below.

- **Daily meditation:** It is very much required everyday soon after returning from the office is to do the meditation for at least one hour. This helps in more resilient to the mental stress.
- Yoga and asanas everyday will improve the health.
- Watch TV programs for an hour which will reduce the mental tension and increases the creativity.
- More and more involvement in any social activities like games, music dance, social service etc.
- The organization should encourage various co-curricular activities in the form of forums and every month or so there should be some entertainment programs.
- A compulsory rest of at least ten days per quarter be given to IT engineers to prepare themselves for the next quarter.
- Planned preparation for the next day's activity is another important stress releasing method.

4. Analysis

It is being observed that most of the IT engineers work like hell for five days a week and other two days they either simply sleep due to exhaust nature or simply enjoy outing. Most of the time they spend their valuable time chatting and other nonproductive activities in the smart phones. Looking into this the HR department now has started some recreation activities to the engineers. The result of this recreation activity is more and more participation by the engineers. But this activity is just limited to the campus inside the company. This is a limitation for the engineers to mingle with the society. This reduces the public contact. This results in lack of general knowledge and what is going on in the society. This is a major problem observed in the IT engineers.

5. Conclusion

This model helps the IT engineers in the following way

1. Relaxed mindset in the working environment
2. Equal priority can be given to the personnel life
3. More and more involvement in co curricular activity.
4. More participation in social activities which enhances ones general knowledge and makes him or her more and more popular in the society.

This model does not permit the engineers to work under pressure. So the company may not like to adopt this policy because the company is interested in commercial aspect which forces the performance of the engineer to reach the goal and is not bothered about the work balance and the personnel life of the engineers. So it is very important to adopt the model to the company in such a way that the company has to encourage more and more engineers to involve in such activities to achieve the work balance in IT industry.

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